

Supplementary Data

Pedigrees:

Pedigree 01:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Pedigree 02:

Gene: *TPM1* c.841A>G p.Met281Val

Pedigree 03:

Gene: *TPM1* c.841A>G p.Met281Val

Pedigree 04:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Gene: *MYH6* c.1960C>T p.Arg654Trp

Pedigree 05:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Pedigree 06:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Gene: *TNNT2* c.832C>T pArg278Cys

Pedigree 07:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Gene: *MYH7* c.3997C>G pLeu1333Val

Pedigree 08:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Gene: *FLNC* c.7657C>T p.Arg2553Trp

Pedigree 09:

Gene: *TPM1* c.841A>G p.Met281Val

Gene: *TTN* c.22832G>T Gly7611Val

Pedigree 10:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Pedigree 11:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Pedigree 12:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Gene: *GLA* c.937G>T p.Asp313Tyr

Pedigree 13:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

Pedigree 14:

Gene: *TPM1* c.62G>T; p.Arg21Leu

